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D10.1 First Interim report on Transnational Access 3

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
TA	Transnational Access
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement

Executive summary

This executive summary provides an overview of the transnational access (TA) activities conducted in Work Package 10 (WP10) TA3 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for everyday living as part of the VITALISE project. The report encompasses seven research infrastructures that participated in this work package, presenting information for both completed TA activities and pending TA activities scheduled for the project's final phase.

The document highlights the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation and advance knowledge in the field of everyday living.

The report includes comprehensive information for each of the participating research infrastructures. For completed TA activities, it provides an analysis of the research conducted, outcomes achieved, and any notable findings or advancements made. This information showcases the value and impact of the TA program on the overall project objectives.

Additionally, the document outlines the pending TA activities that are yet to be carried out during the project's final phase. It includes details such as the planned research objectives, anticipated benefits, and expected outcomes. These pending TA activities represent the project's ongoing commitment to exploring new avenues of research and maximizing the potential of Living Lab infrastructures.

As the first interim report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP10's TA3. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of everyday living. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's outcomes and setting the stage for the comprehensive final report due in month 36.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP10

Work Package 10 (WP10) in the VITALISE project focuses on the centralized and coordinated design and implementation of Transnational Access (TA) for Living Lab infrastructures related to the everyday living domain. TA refers to the utilization of VITALISE infrastructures by researchers located in countries other than where the accessed infrastructure is located. WP10 encompasses several research infrastructures: AUTH's simulated living environment, GAIA's smart spaces, INTRAS' MIND lab, LICALAB's older adults' homes, TREBAG's wellbeing living lab, LAUREA's Activity Living Lab, and AIT's Technology Experience Laboratory. These diverse settings foster research and testing for the everyday living domain.

The support offered during TA visits includes, but is not limited to, logistics management, provision of working space, scientific support by Living Lab researchers for stakeholder management, assistance in preparing and submitting ethical applications, conducting experiments, and technical support for maintenance or resolving technology issues, if necessary.

The TA procedure and manual is handled in WP11 NA4 - Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection. Efforts for outreach to new users are described in WP13, utilizing the project website and existing communication channels of ENoLL, EIT Health LL, and Forum LLSA. Capacity-building activities in WP4 and the calls in WP11 facilitate outreach and selection of approved proposals. The financial support for travel and accommodation provided to researchers is expected to increase transnational access to the infrastructures.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The purpose of the D10.1 "First Interim Report on Transnational Access 3" is to summarize the activities conducted under the VITALISE project's Work Package 10 TA3 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for everyday living. The report includes both completed and pending transnational access activities across seven research infrastructures. It details the research conducted, the outcomes, and significant findings from completed activities, while outlining planned objectives, benefits, and expected results from pending activities. This interim report serves as an essential resource for stakeholders, providing insights into the project's progress and laying the groundwork for the final report, offering preliminary insights that will be further developed and expanded upon in the D10.2 document, the "Final Report on Transnational Access 3." setting the stage for the final report (D10.2, due in month 36, March 2024).

The report is linked to the activities and information collected in the Transactional Accesses of WP8 and WP9, having the same structure as D8.1 "First Interim Report on Transnational Access 1" and D9.1 "First Interim Report on Transnational Access 2".

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structure as such:

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides a description of Work Package 10 (WP10), outlines the purpose of the document, and presents the structure of the report.
- **Section 2 (Finalized Transnational Access Projects)** includes overall evaluation results and for each Living Lab infrastructure. It also provides details for each Transnational Access (TA) project, including the report, evaluation from researchers, and the number of hours spent by the Living Lab personnel, as shown in an Excel spreadsheet.
- **Section 3 (Planning of Upcoming TA Projects)** offers updates on overall planning. For each Living Lab infrastructure, it presents data for each planned TA, such as the project name, planned TA period, Consortium Agreement (CA) signed and uploaded by the

applicants, CA signed by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), CA sent and signed by the applicants, signing of the Beneficiary Agreement (BA, if applicable), initial questionnaires, and visits performed.

- **Section 4 (Conclusion)** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Finalized Transnational Access projects

2.1 Overall evaluation results

This section presents the five research projects that are finalized in this WP10 Transnational Access until the present date.

2.2 AUTH living environment simulation

2.2.1 "ASSURE" project – Carlo Pedrolli (Lead Applicant) (ID34)

2.2.1.1 Project summary

The main focus of the "ASSURE" project (Automatic dysphagia Screening through artificial intelligence) was the assessment of a novel technology based on AI (Artificial Intelligence) that can be used to detect the risk of dysphagia among the elderly population. Dysphagia can be defined as the "medical term for swallowing difficulties". The automatic tool, which is supported by WITA device as software-hardware solution, uses computer vision and artificial intelligence. More specifically, a 3D camera and a digital stethoscope or laryngophone, streamline, through an automatic unsupervised approach, the "The Test of Masticating and Swallowing Solids" (TOMASS) which represents a best clinical practice to screen oral phase dysphagia among older subjects. The same is proposed for the timed Swallow Test (TWST), a dysphagia screening test to screen dysphagia for liquids using the swallowing of 150 ml of tapered water measuring the speed to consume 150 mL of tap water in (mL/s) and comparing it with normative data for age. For all the participants, both TOMASS and TWST were performed and recorded and afterwards, will be analysed within ASSURE project.

The setup simply required the subject to carry on the activities, as defined by TOMASS and TWST, in front of a camera connected to a computer, while wearing a digital stethoscope or laryngophone strapped to the neck, without the need for intervention of specialized clinical staff. The participants of the study were people either with or without mild symptoms of dysphagia.

Prior to the beginning of the test, a complete clinical oral examination was performed, aiming to understand whether the presence of gingival inflammation or the type of the patient's dental formula, may interfere and be confounding factors in the diagnosis of dysphagia and thus may lead to a misdiagnosis of dysphagia.

In addition, prior to the test, the operator started ASSURE software on a PC and filled in the information regarding the gender and age of the participants. Moreover, a clinical history was collected, asking some important clinical data (presence of hypertension, cancer, etc.) and some questions about swallowing liquids and solids, chewings, dentures etc.

Regarding the analysis of the results, an algorithm is projected to auto-score both TOMASS and TWST and the same interpretation is made in a visual way. Afterwards, a comparison is made between scores with visual and video-recorded TOMASS and TWST; an agreement between TOMASS and TWST as visual and video-recording is performed.

For the purposes of this TA, two researchers, Camilla Nocchi from the University of Verona and Simone Segala from the University of Padua visited AUTH Living Environment Simulation in Thessaloniki, Greece, under the supervision of Prof. Carlo Pedrolli. The visiting days were the 3rd of June – 1st of July 2023 for Camilla Nocchi and the 6-23 of June 2023 for Simone Segala. During this period, the two researchers had the opportunity to recruit and perform the test on around 26 participants in total, with the continuous support of the Living Lab's research staff. In addition, the two visiting researchers trained two members of the Living Lab staff, a doctor and a dentist, in order to continue ad hoc the data collection.

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was actually also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), were involved two Ethics & Security Managers, two Administrative & Financial Managers, one technical expert, one doctor, one dentist and some other supportive LL staff (4 more people). In total, approximately 175 hours were spent by all the mentioned professionals for supporting the realization of ASSURE project in AUTH Living environment simulation, both in person and remotely, which is translated to more or less 25 person days.

2.2.1.2 TA Evaluation

Information from the evaluation questionnaires and the final report of this TA are not included in this First Interim report since the study ended recently and they are still pending. They will be included in the next deliverable.

2.3 GAIA Smart Spaces

At this period, GAIA has not performed any transnational access. The TA will be executed by the end of the project and reported in the final version of D10.1. GAIA will include the information regarding the expected TA in the section planning of upcoming TA project.

2.4 INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living

None of the TA projects using the INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living infrastructure has started at this point. A first study is planned for October-December 2023 (ID94) intending to perform case studies of INTRAS Living Lab projects that have the theme of an active life for the elderly with the application of ICTs, for adaptation to the Douro region. The second and third projects are planned for November23-January24 (ID82; ID86), interconnected and envisaging to advance in the work of the MinDNet and finally to adapting the “I Can Do Pathway tool” to Spanish population during co-design sessions and its evaluation.

The information regarding INTRAS expected TA is displayed in the section planning of upcoming TA project.

2.5 LiCalab older adults’ homes

2.5.1 “Releasing the power of users” Project – Judy Hong Huang (ID20)

2.5.1.1 Project summary

The main purpose of the TA were the co-creation sessions with older adults from LiCalab’s user panel to gain insight into the methods for involving users and articulating their voices during the innovation development journey. The preferred method for exploring this question was the User Café, a method derived from the World café, a conversation-based knowledge-sharing method.

Two User Cafés were conducted during this TA in March 2023 concerning the theme “Innovative Products for Daily Life.” Participants were older adults (above 60) recruited by LiCalab from their user panel. During each session, we showcased some innovative Nordic technologies developed to improve the health and well-being of older adults. The older adults were invited to share their opinions regarding the technologies with the group. To facilitate that, we used a template for them to write down their thoughts on post-it notes. The template consisted of four areas: questions (about the technology), (perceived) pros, (perceived) cons, and the (possible) target group. Subsequently, we shared knowledge about the Norwegian healthcare system, including its structure, coverage,

healthcare services for older adults in Norway, etc. Then, we invited participants for a short (10-15 minutes) one-on-one interview, asking them about their experiences attending this event. Each session lasted for three hours. Lunch and coffee were served.

In each session, three innovative digital healthcare technologies targeting older adults were introduced. Most of them were developed by start-ups located in Nordic countries. One example of a technology is a web portal for teaching and helping older adults to use public and private digital services. Another is an e-sport cycling app for older adults and their family members to bike in different scenery. The purpose of showing the technologies was to test the methods for user inclusion rather than test or sell any products. The companies or their physical products were absent during the session. One company provided a demo video for us to play on the tablet and for the older adults to try out during the session. In return, we share insights about the technologies we collected from the participants (on post-it notes).

A total of 25 interviews with 19 unique participants in addition to four interviews with four facilitators were conducted. Participants shared their reasons for joining the activities, opinions, and suggestions on the product and the session. Motivators to participate in the sessions were their willingness to learn about new skills and innovations, meet new people, and contribute to developing technologies that could benefit themselves and others. The "Nordic innovation" was also an exciting topic for them. They were eager to learn about new things. Some even compared it to the Belgian system. They expressed their ideas, including concerns about developing healthcare technologies for older adults, such as safety and the ease/difficulty of using and learning about the new technologies. We saw the importance of understanding the older adults' needs when developing solutions. The focus should be on developing "with" them rather than simply "for" them. Older users are curious about new technologies and are willing to express positive and negative comments after being informed about the importance of their involvement.

In addition to the dedicated User Café sessions defined in the VITALISE proposal, Judy was involved in other pre-planned LiCalab activities. Although most sessions were in Dutch, Judy could observe group dynamics and was engaged in developing co-creation materials and reflecting discussions between facilitators after the sessions.

2.5.1.2 TA evaluation

In the evaluation questionnaire, Judy declares that the output of TA was somewhat higher than expected, even though she had high expectations before the start of the project. In advance, she wished to gain a deeper understanding of the LiCalab's user engagement work, including their co-creation methods & tools with users from different stages of the innovation process, and to gain experiences about living lab practitioners' work in another contextual environment. The inclusion of the fast track training program during TA was perceived very useful. All living lab services provided during TA (understand end-users needs and problems, methodological support and guidance, selection/recruitment of test persons, expertise/support with end-users, physical infrastructure) were rated very high in terms of quality. Key strengths of LiCalab comprised the close relationship with the user community, deep knowledge of methodologies and experience in practice. All within Vitalise developed products (Data tool, Panel management tool, Vitalise website, and Vitalise wiki page) were rated highly useful and user friendly. The Vitalise website was even evaluated as very high in terms of user friendliness. These products were considered an easy to reach and useful resource during the TA project. To summarise, the collaboration between Judy and LiCalab was a success. This was reflected in Judy's second research stay at LiCalab after the Vitalise project. Additionally,

both universities are planning on writing a book chapter together and LiCalab is planning a 3-day visit to Stavanger in Norway in the autumn of 2023 to explore possibilities for future collaborations or partnerships.

Following LiCalab professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one business manager, one operations manager, two panel managers, one scientific coordinator and one researcher/psychologist. In total 101,5 dedicated hours were spent by the aforementioned professionals. This corresponds to 20 days during which the LL staff was working on the project. The two panel managers performed most of these hours (73 hours). Transferring knowledge about panel management was an important goal of this project in addition to testing the user café as method for co-creation sessions with older adults. As the file was filled in retrospectively, was not taken into account the time spent to spontaneous questions asked in between the dedicated time slots. Hence, the amount of hours actually spent on the project might be somewhat higher.

The final report of this TA is included in **Error! Reference source not found. Error! Reference source not found.**

2.6 Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab

2.6.1 “Relationship between physical fitness, physical activity and healthy lifestyle in Seniors” Project – José Carlos Fernández-García (ID27)

2.6.1.1 Project summary

The primary goal of this project was to examine varying levels and manifestations of physical fitness, with a particular emphasis on health and well-being, and to correlate these with lifestyle habits. To achieve this, we engaged 23 elderly individuals from the NWeLL user panel in assessments that took place on the 27th and 29th of June 2023. During these sessions, we gathered health-related data using a precise smart scale (a TANITA Bioimpedancimeter with clinical validity). This allowed us to measure aerobic capacity, flexibility, strength-endurance, dexterity, daily energy intake, as well as nutritional and health-related behaviours. The data regarding healthy lifestyle habits was collected using the internationally validated 'HEALTHY LIFESTYLE QUESTIONNAIRE.

In sum, body composition will be assessed through bioimpedance; physical activity through the IPaQ-7 questionnaire; physical fitness through specific tests described below; and healthy lifestyle habits through the Healthy Lifestyles Questionnaire.

This measurement is going to be followed by an 8 weeks long training for the participants with a highly qualified instructor, and after the 8 weeks Prof. Fernández-García is going to repeat the measurements. Hence, this research is a part of a longitudinal, correlational study, with the purpose to determine the relationship (or degree of association) between two or more concepts, categories or variables in a context, in particular physical activity behaviors and healthy lifestyle habits in adults aged 55 to 80 years.

NWeLL Research Infrastructure provided 23 smart watches for the research participants, allowing us and the external researcher to collect and generate big data throughout the 10-12 weeks of the whole research.

All the participants of the research (mostly women aged 55 to 80 years) are very keen on being part of this study, not only because they got a clearer picture about their physical fitness, but also because they are also provided with the means to develop and train their physical wellbeing.

The following NWeLL professionals were involved in the support of this TA project: one technical research manager, one facilitator, one sport expert, and a data analyst. In total 103 dedicated hours were spent by the professionals. This corresponds to 19 days (about 2 and a half weeks) during which the LL staff engaged with the project. Most of the activities and tasks were connected to guaranteeing the technical/digital conditions of the measurements, and a safe and healthy personal/physical participation of the 40 stakeholders in the research.

2.6.1.2 TA evaluation

Information from the evaluation questionnaires and the final report of this TA are not included in this First Interim report since the study ended recently and they are still pending. They will be included in the next deliverable.

2.7 Laurea Activity Living Lab

None of the TA projects using Laurea Activity Living Lab has started at this point. A first study is planned for starting end of August 2023 (ID45) intending to understanding momentary context by extracting contextual knowledge through analyzing subjective self-reports with the corresponding objective and sensor data. The second project is planned for September 2023 (ID40) oriented to build up tools for clubs and other stakeholders to offer recreational football for participants 60+ years of age. The third project is planned for October 2023, focused in understanding the links between fundamental movement skills and different 'markers' of injury risk and movement capability in children and adolescents who play grassroots sport (ID71).

The information regarding LAUREA expected TA is displayed in the section planning of upcoming TA project.

2.8 AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

2.8.1 "Evaluation of use of technology by informal caregivers" Project – Francesca Gris (ID24)

2.8.1.1 Summary

Starting from the results of the previous project EvAALuation, which has developed and standardized the measuring instruments (questionnaires) for the assessment of AAL technologies from older people perspective, the project developed a new version of the instrument. This new version will be used by informal caregivers of people with dementia and assisted people, to assess their evaluation of the use of the technology in care settings.

The first activity consisted in analysing the existing instrument (structure, constructs and single items), already available in English and German. Every single item was analysed to select which ones fit to caregivers and older people's perspective.

The requested expert and advisory services were used in everyday collaboration with the AIT team. Short meetings and ad-hoc discussions fostered the collaboration with the local research team. The capacity building and networking will allow to share the result with other partner organizations.

As a basis for the follow-up collaboration with the AIT on personal support solutions for informal caregivers of persons with dementia, a new version of the evaluation tool kit was developed. This new version takes into account the perspective of caregivers and older people and in particular their need to fill in short and quick instruments that could be able to assess the impact of the intervention.

A first version of this new instrument consists of two scales: a scale for caregivers, with 34 items; a scale for people with dementia, with 18 items. Items were selected from each of the three areas: health, care and being active, covering aspects like experience in using technology, digital inclusion, privacy, social interaction, need of support.

The existing EvAAUation research instruments are already available to the research community. Work on the adaption of these instruments for measuring the impact of personal support systems for informal caregivers will continue beyond the end of the Transnational Access activity. As soon as they are validated with experts and the target group, these adapted instruments will be made openly accessible for the research community.

For supporting the execution of this TA, the LL manager as well as one facilitator were involved. In total, approximately 84 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the project at the AIT Technology Experience Lab, both in person and remotely, which is translated to approx. 10 person days.

2.8.1.2 TA Evaluation

Overall, this Transnational Access activity was very positively evaluated by the visiting researcher. Services provided by the LL allowed the researcher to achieve the expected outcome.

The results of this project may be useful overall for all the institution that are involved in projects that use technology to support the informal caregivers of people with dementia. Together with the AIT research team, collaboration on personal support systems for informal caregivers will be continued also beyond the end of the Transnational Access activity. Adjusted instruments to assess the impact of such systems will be further developed and released to the research community, especially some partners of host institution (AIT) and home institution (INRCA).

3 Planning of upcoming TA projects

The following sections give an overview and a short description of the upcoming TA projects that will be performed in the WP10 Living Lab infrastructures.

3.1 Overall planning updates

Figure 1: VITALISE TA WP10

The infographic presents the overall results of the VITALISE Transnational Access, where, as it can be observed, 62 researchers from more than 12 countries applied to the open call. From this total of applicants, it is encountered a majority of female applicants (61%). In agreement to WP8 and WP9, most applicants are from academia (65,5%).

3.2 AUTH living environment simulation

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the AUTH upcoming TA projects.

Table 1: Current status of each upcoming TA project in AUTH living environment simulation

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID28	JUL	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
ID31	OCT-NOV	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

ID28. Richard Rak, Università di Bologna. Project: IoT-MH

The present project, named “IoT-MH” (Privacy and Data Protection Challenges Affecting Internet of Things for Mental Health: Comparative Perspectives and Pathways for Soft Regulation in Europe and Canada) aims to analyze whether soft law instruments could address privacy and data protection challenges that are specific to the deployment of IoT devices for mental health. The

research findings intend to contribute to ongoing policy initiatives and discussions on the possible (soft) regulation of e-mental health services.

The study aims to construct inter-jurisdictional perspectives through collaboration with two Living Labs. One of the researchers (Richard Rak, DIGITALEUROPE) will analyze the “EU perspective” of the problem at the AUTH Living Environment Simulation, while another researcher (Elisabeth Steindl, University of Vienna, Department of Innovation and Digitalisation in Law, and Research Platform Governance of Digital Practices) will study the “Canadian perspective” at the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab. The expertise of the staff members of the two Living Labs is indispensable to gather insights into what specific privacy and data protection-related concerns (e.g. legal uncertainties, security risks, data management issues) have emerged in the development and testing of IoT devices for mental health in two different regulatory and research environments. By collaborating with two Living Labs in two different jurisdictions (EU and Canada), the study aims to provide a comparative account of regulatory deficiencies and explore whether and which soft law instruments could facilitate good practices in e-mental health in the EU.

The data for this part of the study framework (i.e. for the analysis of the “European perspective”) will be collected by the researcher (Richard Rak) at AUTH Living Environment Simulation. The researcher will conduct semi-structured interviews with the research staff of the AUTH Living Environment Simulation (Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab), who have experience in developing and using IoT-enabled mental health applications. The objective of the interviews is to collect information about the empirical experiences of researchers working at Living Labs, especially on how they cope with the aforementioned legal, ethical and technological challenges.

Afterwards, the analysis of the data collected in the interviews will take place in 2 stages: a) content analysis of individual interviews; b) comparison, integration and synthesis of content analysis results. For the first step, the researcher will classify the individual answers according to the questions (areas of discussions), evaluating the relevance of the answers to the study. For the second step, the researcher will map recurring answer patterns, and identify any deviating answers.

ID31. Chiorean Claudia (Lead Applicant), Simona Malaescu, Universitatea Babeş-Bolyai, Cluj-Napoca. Project: Multitasking in the Academic digital world

The aim of this study, named ‘Multitasking in the Academic digital world’, is to analyze the relationship between distributive attention, the level of understanding of the text in digital space, the level of stress recorded in multitasking, and the identification of new directions of activity in the primary prevention of the stress involved in burnout for students. The study is relevant in studying the level of understanding of Generation Z students exposed to the danger of burnout. This experiment contributes to the prevention of digital burnout due to multitasking, offering arguments in favor of organizing the activity in the online system and balancing the study time and work time during the student period. The data obtained about the correlation between multitasking and distributed attention, the level of understanding of an online text, and the perceived stress (a main factor of burnout) will be used to establish the need for a balance between online and physical tasks.

The participants of the study will be 18+ students enrolled in programs preparing for professions with online/digital work components or working part-time in such organizations. The study will follow a six stages experiment with pre-testing and post-testing comparing the results of the intervention group with the control group. The first three stages follow the dynamics of comprehension in the multitasking conditions under the impact of 1, 2, and 3 simultaneous stimuli. In the intervention stage (4) the students in the experimental groups will be trained in strategies and

techniques for managing stress in multitasking working conditions and tolerating emotional distress during an oral presentation.

3.3 GAIA Smart Spaces

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the GAIA upcoming TA projects.

Table 2: Current status of each upcoming TA project in GAIA Smart Spaces

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID70	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID73	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID76	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID96	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

ID70. Bar Yitzhaki (lead applicant), Alon Meiri, from Connecteam, Israel. Project: Arts-Smart

Project objective is to generate a Performing Arts-Smart space for dialogue, citizen-centred, generating an open innovation ecosystem based on an inclusive user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in a real-life community and setting.

Concretely, this project wants to prove that practicing Performing arts in Smart public spaces improves considerably not only the physical but also the mental health. Art therapy in-group settings, which is referred to as group art therapy, can be a treatment that combines art and group therapy (Erickson & Young 2010).

Regarding the specific objectives we are looking for, the pandemic caused by the Covid-19 virus has changed many habits that people used to have in public spaces, and one of the challenges has been to give a solution to each of the problems caused. The remarkable objectives are the following:

- i. Analyse the practicing of performing arts in public Smart spaces and using digital media for giving the participants support.
- ii. Give visibility to the technology use for Performing arts in public smart spaces.
- iii. Co-create a new work methodology for projects aimed at practicing in Smart Spaces and recording and promoting through digital media.

ID73. Sara Gonçalves (lead applicant), Flavia Machado, from the start-up Actif, Portugal. Project: Let's get Actif

The present project aims to evaluate the impact of the 2-month use of a digital platform on the cognitive function and functional capacity of healthy older adults.

We hope that through the transnational access to the living labs to have access to the following services: small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, usability testing, co-creation sessions, stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (market and competitor intelligence services).

The main outcomes will be lower body function as measured by the Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB) and cognitive function using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment Scale (MoCA) at baseline, after phase 1 post-intervention, after the washout period and after phase 2 post-intervention. Secondary outcomes will be quality of life (EQ-5D-3L), satisfaction with life (SWLs), gait speed and mobility, respectively measured through the 6-Meters Walk test (6MWT) and the Timed-up-and-Go test (TUG). Additionally, a satisfaction questionnaire about the usage of Actif will be conducted to determine the acceptability, adequacy, satisfaction, user-friendliness, and net promoter score, partially based on the Senior Technology Acceptance and Adoption model (STAM).

ID76. Lorena Serjnjaj (lead applicant), Rezarta Lalo, Jonida Mehmetaj, Klaudja Guga. from University of Vlora "Ismail Qemali", Albania. Project: ArtDDementia

Under the pressure of the latest developments in modern technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, advanced robotics, etc., many industries are changing so rapidly, and they are reshaping in nature and structure. This technological development has influenced the behaviour of individuals in society, the way of doing work, but also the life expectancy of people. The main objective of the project is to evaluate the impact of combining creative arts clinical therapies with vitamin D intake on the health and well-being of elderly people with Alzheimer's disease. The main objective of the project is to evaluate the impact of combining creative arts clinical therapies with vitamin D intake on the health and well-being of elderly people with Alzheimer's disease.

The aim of this TA is to focus on Art therapy and Vitamin D for the prevention of cognitive decline of Alzheimer's disease dementia. The main objective of the project is to evaluate the impact of combining creative arts clinical therapies with vitamin D intake on the health and well-being of elderly people with Alzheimer's disease. A second aim of the research is to investigate the variability in biological parameters (like blood pressure, glucose, cholesterol, and body mass index), creativity parameters and vitamin D intake.

ID96. Francesca Gris, from the Istituto Nazionale di Riposo e Cura Anziani (INRCA), Italy. Project: TAD - Tech and Arts against Dementia.

The aim of this TA is to increase the knowledge of technologies that can be applied to non-pharmacological therapies, especially which use arts (i.e. music, dance, pictures...). To do this, a guide of best practice and innovative ideas will be provided. In addition, the TA will be an opportunity to identify ways of assessing the impact of these good practices, through the use of advanced technological tools.

The first phase of the project benefits from the knowledge of the GAIA Lab technology. The aim of this first phase is to identify possible solutions (already tested or innovative) that can support non-pharmacological interventions based on arts.

The second phase of the project involves a group of stakeholders (family and/or older people with dementia and/or experts in the field of aging), in order to share the identified solutions, according to a co-design approach.

Finally, the third phase of the project aim to create a guide that contains innovative ideas to combine the technological potential to the potential that art can have as a non-pharmacological therapy.

3.4 INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the INTRAS upcoming TA projects.

Table 3: Current status of each upcoming TA project in MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID82	NOV-JAN	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID86	NOV-JAN	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID94	OCT-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

ID82. Kristina Niedderer, Manchester Metropolitan University (Lead Applicant), Jennifer Lim, Erika Renedo Illarregi. Project: MinDNet - Designing for dementia, mental health and wellbeing

This Transnational Access Project proposes to expand on the work initiated by the European MinD project (GA 691001), continuing the interdisciplinary research in the field of design for supporting people living with mental illness, dementia, and neurodiverse conditions, with a focus on wellbeing and mindfulness. The project aims to enhance the recognition and implementation of design's therapeutic potential in healthcare contexts, focusing on co-designing and inclusion of people with lived experience, which is often found to be empowering and healing.

The MinD network, formed by partners of the MinD project, plans to continue promoting the benefits of design in care, health, and policy sectors on an international level. This proposal seeks to support the activities of the MinD network, facilitating research in the application of design in dementia and wellbeing and defining a multidisciplinary strategy to include under-represented minorities. The project aims to refine the network's values and embed them into its formal structure and set the stage for the strategic implementation of its aims, such as training and collaborative initiatives.

The project brings together key individuals, such as Niedderer, the chair of the network, who brings design-led vision and experience, Lim, who has expertise in public health and the inclusion of under-represented minorities, and Illarregi, who specializes in creative and mental health fields. They will collaborate to develop the network strategy, working with experts by experience to ensure their inclusion.

The project will involve data collection on values and methods, network organisation, and training development, with a mode of delivery involving literature and dialogic research. The project will be located at INTRAS, with the team having access to the research and care practice network and a Group of Experts by Experience (GEE), consisting of older adults who contribute their experiential knowledge for innovating for health improvement.

The proposed work is expected to help establish the MinD network strategy, promote the inclusion of Experts by Experience in research and design activities, influence policy to promote holistic, inclusive, and preventive approaches using design to support health and care, and enable the development of support mechanisms for advancing the network. The outputs will be disseminated through the MinD network strategy document, updates on the MinD website, and publications in the public newsletter of Alzheimer Europe.

ID86. Dr. Isabelle Tournier (lead applicant), and Prof. Christine-Vanessa Cuervo-Lombard from the Université Toulouse Jean Jaurès, France, and Prof. Kristina Niedderer from the Manchester Metropolitan University. Project: Span-ICanDo - adapting the I Can Do Pathway tool to Spanish population during co-design sessions, testing the tool.

Span-ICanDo is a project aimed at adapting the I Can Do Pathway tool, a solution facilitating access to and participation in meaningful activities for people living with mild to moderate dementia, to the Spanish population. Initially developed in the UK, the tool will be translated into Spanish, evaluated, and adjusted based on feedback from relevant Spanish stakeholders including those living with mild to moderate dementia and those with subjective cognitive complaints.

The project timeline includes one week for Translating the I Can Do Pathway tool into Spanish, followed by two weeks dedicated to evaluate the translated tool in co-creation workshops involving Spanish people living with mild to moderate dementia and Spanish people with subjective cognitive complaints. Gather their feedback on the tool's potential usefulness and necessary improvements. A final week dedicated to analyse collected data, prepare dissemination supports, and write the final report.

The project will involve two groups of stakeholders: those with "subjective cognitive complaint" and those with "mild to moderate cognitive impairment." Each group will participate in co-design workshops to assess the tool's efficacy and applicability.

The ultimate impact of the project includes making the I Can Do Pathway tool available in Spanish, broadening its potential user base, improving understanding of user characteristics that facilitate the use of such tools, and reinforcing research collaboration with INTRAS, the Living Lab and its innovation ecosystem.

ID94. João Rodrigues (applicant), Helena Morais, Comunidade Intermunicipal do Douro, Portugal. Project: CIM Douro Case Studies - Study for the adaptation of the active ageing model

The project "CIM Douro Case Studies - Study for the adaptation of the active ageing model" is pillared in the value that Douro CIM has consistently found in its involvement in POCTEP projects, gaining knowledge from other territories' innovative methods and refining their own practices through collaboration. Recognizing the unique challenges of their territory, such as low density, aging population, and isolation in rural areas, they have sought measures and solutions to enhance the quality of life for their senior citizens, focusing on promoting safety and combating isolation. To this end, their participation in projects aimed to encourage the creation of products and services for independent living.

INTRAS Living Lab is coordinating different projects focused in the areas of interest and with challenges such as the rurality and the imbalanced distribution of care resources in the community, to which can provide access for on-site observation and participation, so to extract first-hand understanding of different approaches between Portugal and Spain.

Data and Analysis Methodology: The data collection will commence with reviewing reports and documents from similar projects focused in both rural and non-rural elderly homes. Following this, case study methodology will be employed to gather more data through interviews and direct participant observations. The collected data will be analyzed using qualitative techniques, identifying key themes, patterns, and potential cause-effect relationships.

3.5 LiCalab older adults' homes

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the LiCalab upcoming TA projects.

Table 4: Current status of each upcoming TA project in LiCalab older adults' homes

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID56	OCT-NOV 23	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
ID57	OCT23-FEB24	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
ID58	OCT 23	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID60	OCT-NOV 23	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID72	NOV-DEC 23	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID75	NOV 23	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

Note. ID57 combines the use of the LiCalab older adults homes with the THOMAS MORE Motion lab infrastructure.

ID56. Dimitrios Iakovakis, AUTH, Greece. Project: Koios Care application – Monitoring quality of life in individuals with Parkinson 's disease.

Parkinson's Disease (PD) can significantly impact a person's Quality of Life (QoL), affecting their physical, occupational, psychological, and social functioning. As the disease progresses, managing the complexities of living with it can become an increasingly challenging task. Typically, PD patients visit the clinic every six months, which can result in problems such as misdiagnosis and suboptimal care due to the sparse measurements and the subjective tools used. Furthermore, there is no treatment for the disease; the pharmaceutical industry is testing new molecules, but monitoring the effects of the treatment is proven to be a complex task. Finally, current digital solutions (which measure for example tremor) struggle to correctly monitor the effects of the current and potential new treatments on daily life and disease status.

At Koios Care, the mission is to improve care for people with PD by passively collecting data from their daily lives and employing artificial intelligence (AI) for interpretation. To achieve this, the research team is developing a unique digital experience for the patients and their healthcare teams. Koios Care founders have extensive research and technological expertise in the domain and have

developed solutions that make use of commonly used technology, such as the Android smartwatch and smartphone, to capture key aspects of QoL for PD patients. The Koios Care solution can be used (a) by pharmaceutical companies to validate the effects of therapies under test, (b) by clinicians to improve collaboration and decision-making, and finally, (c) by patients to passively monitor aspects of daily life. In this project, we aim to analyze the user-acceptance of the Koios Care application suite. To do this, a validated technology that assesses QoL will be tested using everyday life data.

ID57. Oonagh Giggins (Lead applicant), Suzanne Smith, Dundalk Institute of Technology, Dublin Road, Dundalk, Co Louth, Ireland. Project: Physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women.

This research seeks to address the issue of physical inactivity and functional decline in mid-life-menopausal women. Physical inactivity is a global health issue, with one in four adults not meeting the recommended target levels for physical activity. Physical activity is reported to decline with advancing age, and middle-aged women are more vulnerable to become physically inactive with the menopausal transition. Regular physical activity results in many health benefits and is an important determinant of physical performance. Poor physical performance is a predictor of frailty, disability and loss of independence and the menopause transition has been shown to be associated with decreased functioning.

The aim of this TA is to examine physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women and examine whether the menopause is associated with an accelerated decline in physical function and physical activity levels and increased musculoskeletal issues.

The project has the following objectives: i. to undertake an examination of physical capability among mid-life (peri-menopausal, menopausal, or post-menopausal) women; ii. to capture a quantitative physical capability dataset in the cohort using body worn sensors and compare sensor measurements with measurements obtained using traditional means; iii. to characterize daily physical activity levels in the same cohort over a 3-month period; iv. to examine differences in physical capability, physical activity and musculoskeletal issues across menopausal stages

This research will firstly involve a cross-sectional study and then a subsequent longitudinal study, to determine the physical activity levels and physical capability of a cohort of mid-life women who are also experiencing musculoskeletal problems.

Data collection: i. Demographics; ii. Physical health: heart rate at rest, blood pressure, weight, body mass index and percentage body fat. Self-reported past medical history (including obstetric and gynaecologic history), use of medications, presence of musculoskeletal disease or conditions, lifestyle related factors (smoking habits, alcohol consumption and daily physical activity levels); iii. Quality of life: Menopause Rating Scale (MRS); iv. Pain: the McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ); v. Menopause status (WHO classifications); vi. Physical capability tests: Timed Up & Go Test (TUG), the 6-minute walk test (6MWT), postural stability tests, gait speed tests, and grip strength test; vii. Physical activity: Withings smart watch: Daily physical activity levels (step count) and sleep

ID58. Suzanne Smith, Oonagh Giggins, Julie Doyle, NetwellCASALA at Dundalk Institute of Technology, Ireland. Project: Identify and learn new types of potential living lab engagements and methodologies

Collaborative engaged learning has a role to play in how living labs interact with stakeholders but is also an effective approach to transfer learning about living lab methodologies and processes. The objective of the learning visit is to share knowledge and experiences about living lab, panel, and project management as well as stakeholder orchestration. The aim is to enhance the regional reach of the NetwellCASALA lab and develop a co-working relationship with LiCalab for potential future collaborations.

Collected data: Qualitative observational data will be collected from diverse pre-planned LiCalab activities. The data topics will include: how LiCalab manages and engages with panel members and in single stakeholder activities, how activities with multiple stakeholders present are orchestrated, and how integration is managed for projects with home and laboratory or health provider elements.

ID60. Claire Kemlin, Lifebloom, France. Project: Usability testing of Lifebloom One in a Rehabilitation Environment

Lifebloom is an industrial medtech that conceives a technology to enable mobility impaired users to stand up and walk on their own. A solution so users can live upright, stay in shape and remain in charge of their lives. Our solution name: Lifebloom One.

The research aims to study the usability of Lifebloom One by mobility impaired adults in a rehabilitation setting. Participants will learn how to use Lifebloom One during 3 to 5 sessions. The ones able to walk on their own will then be encouraged to use Lifebloom One in their everyday lives for at least one week (rehabilitation setting). Usability data will be collected as well as feedback from participants and healthcare professionals.

ID72. Mark Plumbley, Thomas Deacon, Arshdeep Singh, Gabriel Bibbó, David Frohlich, University of Surrey, UK. Project: "Sound Wellbeing in Later Life": Exploring wellbeing through contextual understanding of sound and sonic reminiscence.

The AI for Sound (AI4S) project aims to improve the wellbeing of older adults in their homes by developing AI sound sensing technologies. The study focuses on two objectives: understanding sound contexts and sonic reminiscence technologies. The project seeks to understand individuals' relationships to sounds and sonic memory in the home, focusing on sound preferences, linking sounds to domestic activities and routines, exploring what people want from AI sound technologies, gathering reflections on memorable daily moments and the sounds in them, and asking what people want to remember. Through in-the-wild research and co-design activities, AI4S aims to understand when, why, and how people would engage with AI sound technologies. Using a data capture deployment pilot, AI4S can analyse sounds in the home to develop technical innovations and data insights related to understanding sound contexts. The research from co-design can help gain a deeper understanding of user needs, desires, and expectations around AI sound technology in the home, informing the development of sonic reminiscence technologies to support emotional wellbeing. Our vision is to develop personal informatics technologies that enable us to capture and interact with sonic memories throughout our life journeys, from youth to old age

ID75. Janette Hughes, Digital Health & Care Innovation Centre, Scotland [under the condition of approval by the scientific evaluation committee]. Project: Readiness tools to accelerate innovation from R&D to service exploitations

Economic development and commercial innovation for Digital health and care is a massive opportunity with the option to drive economic growth through living labs methodology. However, it

remains challenging for Digital health and care related innovators to converge business and service readiness support, and without this is remains a recognised key barrier. The Digital Health and Care innovation centre in Scotland and through the Rural centre of excellence Living Labs utilise an elementary technology, service and business readiness which relates to the service readiness level research (Hughes, 2021) that has evolved over recent years. This readiness framework is used by DHI as a baselining, scoping, and evidence related tool/checklist. It also acts as a useful conversation prompt for all stakeholders to understand their current status and the steps and evidence (Hughes, 2021) they need to gather to build a business case for scale, where and if digital can be embedded within a service. In addition, this tool importantly allows industry and commercial activities need to be covered to reach a commercial sale for this sector in line with the use of Living Lab methodology. This project will explore with other LL partners if similar tools can be merged to meet the pressing need of faster commercialisation for this sector.

3.6 Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the Nagykovácsi LL upcoming TA projects.

Table 5: Current status of each upcoming TA project in Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID30	SEPT-OCT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID85	PENDING	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID91	PENDING	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

ID30. Efstathios Christodoulides and Olivia Tsivitanidou. Project: VR for Seniors well-being.

The purpose of the ‘VR for Seniors well-being’ project is twofold: (i) to make VR technologies, their use and practical application accessible to senior citizens, especially those with fewer opportunities to use digital technologies and/or few or no competences in the use of VR and promote their increased participation in VR experiences that promote an active and healthy lifestyle; (ii) measure the impact of an intervention targeting senior citizens, involving the use of VR technologies, on their technology acceptance and physical fitness. For doing so, a two-week intervention will be organized and implemented, targeting VR senior citizens. During the intervention, the participants will be engaged in a series of VR sessions, with the guidance and support of the researcher. Pre- and post-intervention data will be collected, measuring participants’ technology acceptance and parameters of physical fitness exploiting the infrastructure of the host organization.

ID85. Anna Lipert and Bartosz Tarkowski. Project: The effect of healthy lifestyle and friendly environment on mental health of elderly people.

The research aims to evaluate the impact of various relaxation techniques and trainings on the cognitive function and stress symptoms of elderly individuals. It seeks to analyse the environmental factors that influence healthy behaviours, identify healthy habits among the elderly population, and

examine the prevalence of depressive and anxiety symptoms. The study also aims to explore the relationship between cognitive functions, healthy habits, and environmental conditions in the elderly. Additionally, the research will assess stress levels among the elderly and evaluate the effectiveness of relaxation techniques in reducing stress symptoms and enhancing cognitive functioning.

The study will involve men and women aged 55 years and above without severe health conditions. Participants will be recruited with the support of the Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab. They will be asked to engage in five different types of relaxation trainings, supervised by a psychologist and certified music therapist specializing in stress reduction techniques, on five consecutive days of the week. Pre- and post-data will be collected at the beginning and end of the study, as well as before and after each training. The participants will also receive educational materials on improving dietary and lifestyle habits, along with a Self-Observation Diary to track their activities during and after the research. After one month, a follow-up questionnaire will be sent to assess potential changes in the participants' lifestyles. Written consent forms will be obtained from all participants.

Data will be collected using various methods, including anthropometric and socio-demographic questionnaires, the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ-SF), FitBit to measure physical activity, the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-42), MOCA test for cognitive functioning, Trail Making Test ver. A and B, number picking test for focus and memory functions, eating habits questionnaire, smoking and alcohol drinking assessment, specially designed environmental condition questionnaire, cortisol and DHEA-S level measurements in saliva samples as biological markers of stress, brain activity measurement using MUSE headband during relaxation trainings, and heart rate monitoring using FitBit.

ID91. José Pedro Amoroso. Project: VALUES2ALL: Tackling Values through Sports.

The research aims to introduce flying disc sports, particularly Ultimate and Sport Disc, to Physical Education (PE) teachers across different EU member countries. The primary objective is to raise awareness about the sport and its associated benefits, such as the Spirit of the Game (SOTG), which promotes values aligned with European values of equality, peace, inclusion, and health. By fostering sportsmanship and ethical conduct, the project intends to use sports as a means for peace and inclusion in the long term.

The methodology involves the participation of PE teachers and coaches as the main participants. Local forums will be organized in partner countries to facilitate discussions and exchange ideas, followed by focus groups to co-design training materials specific to each country. A digital questionnaire will measure the acceptance and usability of a digital tool related to SOTG. Functional testing of fundamental motor skills will analyze the impact of disc sports on children's development, particularly throwing techniques. Data generated from these procedures will be analyzed to derive meaningful insights and conclusions.

The research aims to create maximum visibility and public awareness of the project activities. The dissemination and exploitation strategy includes engaging the target group and key stakeholders, establishing policy dialogues, promoting project events, and maintaining a strong online presence. The research aims to enhance PE education by integrating flying disc sports into school curricula, promoting physical activity, inclusion, diversity, and European values. By involving stakeholders from the start and generating engagement through various events, the project seeks to leave a lasting impact on PE education and students' experiences. The results will be shared through National Federations to Schools and Clubs and with the support of stakeholders and partnerships.

3.7 Laurea Activity Living Lab

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the Laurea upcoming TA projects.

Table 6: Current status of each upcoming TA project in Laurea Activity Living Lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID40	SEP	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
ID45	AUG	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
ID71	OCT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO

ID40. Melanie BOITHIAS, Alain BELLI, Emma GUILLET-DESCAS, France. Project: 6-0!+ recreational football for 60+ old participants

The project's object is to build up tools for clubs and other stakeholders to offer recreational football for participants 60+ years of age as well as to harmonize already existing methods and produce some new data for stakeholders to use. Project will seek citizen 60+ years of age regardless of gender to participate. The aim is to target 25-30 participants. Training are held twice a week and will follow the 6-0! training regimen. Prior the activities a co-creation workshop will be arranged to the stakeholders to formulate the project activity sessions. The idea is to hear the stakeholders (participants, **local** club representative, and municipality representative) point of views for such an activity. After the activity is over, a new co-creation session will be organized to improve and finalize the project concept. During the onsite visit researchers will participate to the training sessions and organize workshop for participants. The ethical approval is OK with minor modifications. Contract agreements are expected to be signed on August by latest. Research visit are planned for week 37 or 38.

ID45. Alireza KHANSAN, Eindhoven University of Technology, Netherlands. Project: CKE (Contextual Knowledge Extraction)

"Understanding momentary context by extracting contextual knowledge through analyzing subjective self-reports with the corresponding objective and sensor data" (Contextual Knowledge Extraction = CKE) project goal is to collect longitudinal physiological sensory data and self-reporting subjective data with pre-configured plug-and-play smartwatch technology. The study seeks a combination of 10 healthy youth and elderly people with a balanced gender. During the study participants' behaviors, thoughts, and feelings are collected (e.g. questions regarding the emotion valence, arousal, positive-affect negative-affect) as well as inquiries to perform specific body activities (e.g., rotate your wrist a few times). Smartwatch will collect various physiological sensory data such as PPG, accelerometry, heart rate, peak-to-peak interval, and pedometer information (number of steps, body activity type, calories burnt, and speed). The collected sensor data and the self-reports are analysed to find potentially meaningful correlations between the objective sensor data and subjective self-reports. Contract agreements have been signed and ethical application is approved. Research visit is planned for week 34.

ID71. Michael DUNCAN, Matteo CROTTI, Ricardo MARTINS, Lucas GUIMARÃES-FERREIRA, Caoimhe TIERNAN, from the Coventry University, UK. Project: MovSkill - Movement Skills for Health and Injury Prevention in Grassroots Sport

“Movement Skills for Health and Injury Prevention in Grassroots Sport” project objective is to understand the links between fundamental movement skills and different ‘markers’ of injury risk and movement capability in children and adolescents who play grassroots sport. Project develops testing and validation activity with stakeholders and via proof of concept and feasibility testing, assess links between an array of different assessment tools used to screen movement and injury risk. The study seeks boys and girls (50-60 participants) who are current engaged in grassroots football, who are ‘apparently healthy’ and aged 10-15 years of age. Parents of participants would also be invited to be involved given the participatory nature of the proposed activities. Movement skills and injury risk measurement tools includes, the Test of Gross Motor Development-3 (TGMD-3Ulrich), Landing Error Scoring System (LESS, Padua et al., 2009), Functional Movement Screen (Cook, et al., 2014), and measures of leg to leg asymmetry via 10-20m sprint speed, counter movement jump assessment and Y-Balance test (Fort- Vanmeerhaeghe et al 2020). Qualitative data on the acceptability and useability of the different tools is also collected from participants and their parents. Ethical approval application will be sent to committee by August 8th. Research visit is planned for week 43. Contract agreements are expected to be signed on August by latest.

3.8 AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

This section presents a summary and the overall status of the AIT upcoming TA projects.

Table 7: Current status of each upcoming TA project in AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID83	OCT/NOV 2023	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID90	SEP 2023	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO

ID83. Lynne Bailie, Professor of Computer Science, School of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, Heriot-Watt University, UK. Project: BCI & SARS for Rehabilitation

Around 80% of acute Stroke and brain injury survivors have an upper limb impairment, limiting the movement of the arm and this impairment, which often persists over the long term (> 12 months), massively affects their activities of daily living. Socially Assistive Robots (SARs) are an emerging technology in the rehabilitation domain. The project aims at developing and validating a SAR-based system for upper-limb motor rehabilitation, which understands user motor intention through Brain-Computer-Interface (BCI) and mimics exercises to help motivate recovery and assess other factors of the interaction such as usability and trust. We argue that the ability to mimic user movement in real-time is important as, with self-managed recovery, people will typically go at their own pace and often mix up exercise routines, removing the ability for the robot to predict future actions.

The objectives of the project are: 1) Develop a system combining a BCI and a SAR for use during upper-limb rehabilitation and 2) Run a pilot test to individually validate the separate components of the system (a) BCI data can be reliably and accurately used to perceive user’s exercise intention, b) Mimicking user movement in real-time has some positive effect towards the user’s motivation to use the system, as well as the perceived trust towards the SAR.

It is planned to use EEG sensing to enable BCI control of a socially assistive robot, utilising both physiological sensing equipment and an embodied robot agent. Using these technologies in an assisted living lab will closely replicate a real-world scenario, creating more accurate datasets, and replicable results for future in-situ deployments. Target group are 15-30 participants consisting of a combination of physiotherapists and individuals recovering from hemiparesis because of conditions such as brain injury or stroke who are undertaking self-managed upper-limb rehabilitation.

ID90. Raluca Sfetcu, psychologist at the Romanian Alzheimer Society. Project: P-ESM-EdI - Protocol for the use of ESM in conjunction with educational interventions for caregivers of PwD.

Informal caregivers of persons with dementia (PwD) frequently experience significant fluctuations in their caregiving burden, often referred to as "good and bad days." Traditional questionnaires that capture average experiences may overlook these fluctuations. To address this gap, the experience sampling method (ESM) offers a valuable approach by collecting data repeatedly in real-life contexts. ESM enables the exploration of day-to-day variations in burden among informal dementia caregivers and facilitates the identification of factors associated with these fluctuations.

As previous research has shown that caregivers with a higher education level, more sense of competence in caring for the PwD, and higher levels of mastery appeared to be less prone to experiencing negative affect when they encountered minor disturbances in daily life (Knippenberg et al., 2018), we want to develop and test a protocol for using ESM in conjunction with educational interventions to more dynamically assess the impact of these type of interventions (e.g. information provision, training programs, educational apps).

The aim of this project is to develop and pilot in a small sample of caregivers of PwD a protocol for the use of ESM in conjunction with educational interventions to gain a comprehensive understanding of daily experiences, emotions, challenges, and coping strategies in their natural environment. By employing ESM, we aim to capture real-time data to investigate the dynamic aspects of caregiving and provide valuable insights into the caregivers' well-being and support needs.

The initial phase of the project will consist of developing an ESM protocol for use with caregivers of PwD in conjunction with educational interventions. The final stage of the project will involve 5-10 volunteer participants to pilot the developed ESM protocol.

Currently, the utilization of ESM in gerontological research, particularly concerning the well-being of dementia caregivers within caregiving settings and their work-life balance, has been relatively restricted. Developing a protocol for use of ESM in conjunction with educational intervention can contribute on the long term to the development of more effective of educational interventions for caregivers of PwD, especially in terms of reducing negative emotionality and burden of care.

4 Conclusion

This document presents an overview about the performed and upcoming TA activities to seven research infrastructures that participate in this work package, highlighting the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation and advance knowledge in the field of transitional care.

As the first interim report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP10's TA3. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of transitional care. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes and setting the stage for the comprehensive final report due in month 36 (March 2024).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

5 Annexes

5.1.1 Final Report Project: ID20 - Releasing the power of users

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

Report for Transnational Access

(Version 1.0, Jan 2023)

Introduction

This is the **Report for Transnational Access** (TA) to be used for reporting the activities you have performed during your TA in one of the VITALISE Living Lab. Please remember that it is mandatory to fill in this report entirely with the required information in order to receive the refund for the expenses covered for your TA.

For teams only

Specify the roles of each person of the teams during TA.

	Name and Surname	Role
1	Judy Hong Huang	Researcher

Describe the activities that you conducted (up to 1 page)

The main purpose of the TA was the co-creation sessions with older adults from LiCalab’s user panel to gain insight into the methods for involving users and articulating their voices during the innovation development journey. The preferred method for exploring this question was the User Café, a method derived from the World café, a conversation-based knowledge-sharing method with large groups. The User Café method had been previously used for articulating users’ needs in Releasing the Power of Users, the research project I belong to in Norway. There is no strict format for a User Café. It is flexible and customizable. Still, it usually has fewer participants than the World café and is relatively slow-paced, making it perfectly suitable for older adults. A typical setup includes introductory presentations (plenary), small group discussions, and plenary meetings. Each session of User Café has a specific theme. The length of each activity varies, but one User Cafe generally lasts two to three hours. Participants are encouraged to socialize. Coffee and refreshments are served.

Two User Cafés were conducted during this TA in March 2023 concerning the theme “Innovative Products for Daily Life.” Participants were older adults (above 60) recruited by LiCalab from their user panel. During each session, we showcased some innovative Nordic technologies developed to improve the health and well-being of older adults. The older adults were invited to share their opinions regarding the technologies with the group. To facilitate that, we used a template for them to write down their thoughts on post-it notes. The template consisted of four areas: questions (about the technology), (perceived) pros, (perceived) cons, and the (possible) target group. Subsequently, we shared knowledge about the Norwegian healthcare system, including its structure, coverage, healthcare services for older adults in Norway, etc. Then, we invited participants for a short (10-15 minutes) one-on-one interview, asking them about their experiences attending this event. Each session lasted for three hours. Lunch and coffee were served.

The technologies were from companies located in Nordic countries, developing digital healthcare technologies for older adults and the public. Most of them were start-ups. One example of technology is a web portal for teaching and helping older adults to use public and private digital services. Another is an e-sport cycling app for older adults and their family members to bike in different scenery. The Releasing of Power of Users project collaborated (or still is collaborating) with the companies, and some of them participated in the past User Cafés in Norway. We, the LiCalab team and I, first had a preliminary meeting in early March to review the technologies and ensure they matched the theme. We picked six companies (anonymized), so three for each session. After that, I contacted the companies explaining the purpose and plan for the User Cafés and inviting “participation”. This time, the purpose of showing the technologies was to test the methods for user inclusion rather than test or sell any products. The companies or their physical products were absent during the session. Therefore, there was a low level of active participation required from them. Still, some companies were very supportive, including one that provided a demo video for us to play on the tablet and for the older adults to try out during the session. In return, we share insights about the technologies we collected from the participants (on post-it notes).

For the first session, on the 21st of March, 14 older adults aged between 65 and 85 were recruited. Participants were divided into three groups and stayed with the same group during the entire session. There were three rounds (represented by three tables), each lasting for 20 minutes. At every table, a facilitator showcased a product and invited them to share their comments which were summarized

using post-it notes. After one table, the group moved to the next one. After a short break, I gave a presentation about the Norwegian healthcare system. At the end, facilitators invited participants to a one-on-one structured interview.

In the second session, on the 28th of March, 13 older adults aged between 65 and 85 participated. Six of them had also been engaged in the first session. In general, this session followed the same format as the previous one - three products, group discussions, plenary feedback, a presentation on Norwegian healthcare, and one-on-one interviews. One main difference was that the participants were randomly assigned each round to a group, so they were with a different group at each table. Towards the end, facilitators invited all participants, including those who had been to the first session, to a one-on-one structured interview.

The language used during the introduction and discussion was Dutch. The presentation explaining the Norwegian healthcare system was in English. Many participants were fluent in English, which made direct exchanges, questions, and answers in English possible. I also ran a one-on-one post-interview with all facilitators. All participants and facilitators signed the consent form beforehand, and we followed the necessary steps to ensure their privacy.

Check the services you used during your TA

Please check all the services you used during the TA.

SERVICES	USED
Networking and Capacity building	
Capacity building	
Equipment and facility rental service	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Grant writing and funding application support service	
Temporary research funding	
Innovation network orchestration	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Marketing and sales support	
Panel management	x
Public procurement support services	
Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	
Project planning and management	
Intake and matching	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Temporary research funding	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Living lab project planning and management	
Panel management	x
Market and competitor intelligence services	
Access to data	
Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	
Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	

SERVICES	USED
Co-creation	
Co-creation session	X
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Public procurement support services	
Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	
Testing and Validation	
Clinical trials	
Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Idea selection and testing	
Impact assessment and validation test	
Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	
Prototyping test	
Simulation test	
Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	
Usability testing	
Advisory services	
Public procurement support services	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Marketing and sales support	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Marketing and sales support	
Public procurement support services	
Other services (please indicate which)	
...	

Describe how you use these services, technologies and tools to carry out your research project (0,5 page)

LiCalab panel managers recruited participants for the two co-creation sessions by publishing a call in LiCalab's monthly newsletter, updating their social media platforms, and sending personal invitations to panel members aged 60 years and above living in the neighbourhood. They also managed tasks related to the participants, e.g., the Dutch informed consent and communication through their panel management platform. We discussed and decided on the themes, technologies, details of the actual arrangement of the day, venue set-up, etc. The sessions were conversational, so we mainly needed a room, a big screen, tables, chairs, pens, post-it notes & clip charts, laptops & tablets (), food & drinks. LiCalab supplied and helped to prepare all these materials.

The facilitators, including three panel managers and one business manager, showcased the technologies and supported the group discussions. Depending on the product, they performed different tasks during the showcasing, such as demonstrating a company website, playing a product demo video on the tablet, or following a video to do physical movements. I sent the information, such as information about the previous Use Cafés in Norway, the agenda, and links for websites, videos, and apps, to the facilitators beforehand.

LiCalab facilitators ran one-on-one structured interviews (in Dutch) with the participants at the end of each session. They translated the Norwegian Healthcare system slides into Dutch for showing on the big screen while I was presenting. They also transcribed and translated the interview voice recordings and the post-it notes from group discussions (from Dutch to English).

Describe the results achieved (0,5 page)

A total of 25 interviews with 19 unique participants in addition to four interviews with four facilitators were conducted. Participants shared their reasons for joining the activities, opinions, and suggestions on the product and the session. Motivators to participate in the sessions were their willingness to learn about new skills and innovations, meet new people, and contribute to developing technologies that could benefit themselves and others. The "Nordic innovation" was also an exciting topic for them. Again, they were eager to learn about new things. Some even compared it to the Belgian system. They expressed their ideas, including concerns about developing healthcare technologies for older adults, such as safety and the ease/difficulty of using and learning about the new technologies. Switching groups in the second session also stimulated discussions on how to ensure participants in a more equal and engaging way. We received positive feedback from the participants too. Facilitators also shared their experiences regarding the organisation of these two sessions, including reflections on the User Café method and suggestions for further improvement. They also mentioned that they learned a few things, such as the small-group format and user interviews, to apply in their future co-creation sessions.

Here are some quotes from the participants below.

"The invitation triggered me. I am curious about new things. Also, the topic of health interests me."

"I am very interested in innovation, and I want to prepare for the future when I'm older and might need some sort of technology to support me. That is also why I participate in a lot of activities."

"I liked the discussion in small groups. Everybody could express their opinion. You can learn a lot from each other. Every round, the same questions were asked. That is good so that you know what to expect."

LiCalab translated the post-it notes collected from the group discussions. From there, we could have an overview of the participants' attitudes and interest areas about the technologies. We saw the

importance of understanding the older adults' needs when developing solutions. to the focus should be on developing "with" them rather than simply "for" them. Older users are curious about new technologies and are willing to express positive and negative comments after being informed about the importance of their involvement.

How do you plan to disseminate the results of your research? (0,5 page)

Describe the dissemination and communication measures applied and that you intend to apply to maximise the impact of your project and the target group(s) addressed.

There are several ways of dissemination. The main one is expected to be a journal article in the innovation field related to topics like Responsible Research and Innovation, sustainable innovation, user innovation, etc., to inform researchers about our findings. Part of the data could be included as a book chapter in an open-access book (in planning, targeted to be completed in 2024) of our research project on user inclusion in developing healthcare technologies. Another is to share the results during a workshop at the Open Living Lab Days 2023 in Barcelona, where we would like to run a User Café with the conference participants. We plan to share our work with the extended network of the Releasing the Power of Users project. We also plan to make video clips about these User Cafés for sharing on LiCalab's digital platforms.

Will you allow open access of the collected data? (Y/N)

If you agreed with your RILs not to allow open access of the collected data, please briefly describe/state the reason why.

Yes.

Do you intend to commercialise the research results?

Within VITALISE we would like to depict the commercialization potential of the Transnational Access activities. It is mandatory to complete both surveys:

- https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/VITALISE_IR_TAs_VAs
- [KTH Tool](#)

(Please download the second survey (excel file), save it locally and send it along with your report with a file name "KTH_VITALISE_TA_[NAME_SURNAME]")

No, we don't intend to commercialise the research results. We don't own any or join the development process of technologies that were showed during the co-creation sessions. We are researching the methods for user inclusion, so the "tangible" outcome of the research is expected to be publications and communication (refer to point 5 dissemination).